

Current Review on Human Trafficking and Migrant Smuggling

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To cite this article: Tufan Akçagöz, St. Clements University, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 6-3, 2022, p. 01-211. - 0099-0001-2206-0401

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ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

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Abstract

In the last few decades, important decisions have been taken by the states as well as developments in many issues, including globalization and transnational crime and terrorism. In addition, there are some questions and problems that the increasing concern about security problems bring next to it. It is not a coincidence that these decisions and developments to shape migration policies and priorities of states do not fall from the agenda of many to migrate. As this rise to the top ranks, the borders should be tightened and regulated to keep unwanted, high-risk migrants away from potential target countries. However, transnational crimes such as human trafficking and immigrant smuggling are increasingly defined as border security problems. This article examines how and to what extent the interventions necessary for human trafficking and smuggling with border control are fundamental. The aim is to place the debate into the relevant ties within the security elements of wider globalization and migration. Human trafficking and immigrant smuggling are complex phenomena that affect people in unusual ways. Sometimes it is linked, but they are separate crimes. It involves the recruitment, transport, or hosting of people to exploit human trafficking, sexual exploitation, forced employment, slavery or taking organs. Victims can be children or adults, boys, girls, boys or women, and trade using inappropriate ways such as threat or use, fraudulent plans, deception, or abuse of power. It can occur within a country or beyond boundaries. Therefore, human trafficking is characterized by an action (employment, transport, transfer, hosting, or delivery), specific tools (threat or power use, deception, fraud, abuse of authority, or abuse of the vulnerable state of one). exploitation (eg, sexual exploitation, forced employment, slavery or taking organs).

Keywords: *Migrant Smuggling, Human Trafficking, Border Safety, Human Smuggling*

1. Introduction

In the literature, it is seen that researchers have conducted many studies with the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Southeast Asia and Pacific Regional Center. Based on

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these studies, it should be considered that each state has the sovereign right to control its own border and regulate immigration. Because the rights of human immigrants should also be considered within this realpolitik. However, this claim is highly political and controversial. In our article, we explore some of the tensions and contradictions that have arisen in this debate. Then it is worth noting that it is possible for states to combine managed migration and strict border controls with the protection of human rights in the current context. Different reflections of globalization in this respect are also included in our article.

2. Differences Between Human Smuggling and Immigrant Smuggling

Unlike human smuggling, which can take place both at home and abroad, smuggling of migrants is a crime that is committed only across borders. Helping immigrants to illegally enter or stay in a country for financial or material gain refers to these crimes. Smugglers make a profitable business out of immigrants' need and/or desire to enter a country and the lack of legal documents to do so. International law requires governments to criminalize migrant smuggling. However, it is necessary to evaluate smugglers separately in this context. Immigrants are not considered to be victims in absolute terms because they consent to the smuggling attempt, mostly due to the lack of regular migration routes. However, undocumented immigrants are often put in dangerous situations (such as dangerous sea crossings) by smugglers and may therefore become victims of other crimes, including serious human rights violations, in the smuggling process.

Human trafficking and migrant smuggling are complex phenomena that affect people in diverse ways. While sometimes linked, these are separate offenses. Human trafficking includes the recruitment, transportation, or housing of people for the purposes of exploitation, such as sexual exploitation, forced labor, slavery, or organ removal. Victims can be children or adults, boys, girls, men, or women, and are trafficked through threats or the use of inappropriate means such as the use of force, fraudulent schemes, deception, or abuse of power. It can occur within a country or across borders. Thus, human trafficking is characterized by an action (recruiting, transporting, transferring, harboring, or receiving people), specific means (threat or use of force,

deception, fraud, abuse of power or abuse of one's vulnerable position). This includes exploitation (for example, sexual exploitation, forced labor, slavery, or organ removal).

3. A Different Look at Migrant Smuggling

Unlike human smuggling, which can take place both at home and abroad, smuggling of migrants is a crime that is committed only across borders. It consists of helping immigrants illegally enter or stay in a country for financial or material gain.

Human trafficking for organ smuggling appears to be a major problem based on anecdotal evidence from law enforcement. It is about creating a human commodity and then using that person for profit through labor, sexual services, or other forms of exploitation. Immigrant smuggling deals with the relationship between a person who wants to immigrate but cannot legally do so, and a person or group that provides criminal services. The immigrant chooses an irregular method and a service provider who is a smuggler. A fee is paid for illegally crossing a border. The immigrant is free to go, at least in theory. These are the main differences, but often immigrants who choose this method to move from one country to another are very vulnerable. They do not have any legal status in their destination country, immigrants who often do not speak the language often have few sources of income or support in their country of origin and are hunted by human traffickers. Often, immigrants find themselves in debt to the arrangers of their immigration.

4. Increasing Understanding of Human Trafficking

Immigrants take enormous personal risks when they put themselves in the hands of smugglers. Immigrants take enormous personal risks when they put themselves in the hands of smugglers. Over the last 25 years, our understanding of the phenomenon of human trafficking has increased. They now recognize that human trafficking is not just about sex, but also includes other ways in which people can be exploited in all sectors of the economy. This is the case, for example, in construction, agriculture, or inside factories, indeed wherever there is a need for large numbers of low-skilled, low-paid manual workers. One of the challenges with forced labor

is identifying when exploitative working conditions shift a balance that becomes a criminal case for human trafficking. There are very few prosecutions and convictions for human trafficking cases, partly because it is a difficult crime to prove. However, it is not unusual for a person trafficked for the purpose of sexual exploitation to be prosecuted for crimes such as rape. This case, which is easier to prove, is easier to understand for the judges and is not so complicated. Human trafficking may be the subject of a prosecution. Rights-based and victim-centered approaches are the basis of these.

With migrant smuggling, it would be appropriate to focus on the people who organize their illegal movements from the migrants themselves. It is necessary to emphasize the need to criminalize immigrants. Immigrants take a huge personal risk when transported by smuggling networks. According to horror stories in the Mediterranean and elsewhere in the world, hundreds of people die behind trucks or in unseaworthy boats. We acknowledge that the pressures on migration will not decrease in the coming years but will increase. Therefore, criminal networks would continue to seek profit by facilitating irregular migration. Immigrant smuggling and trafficking in persons linked to irregular migration will continue to be significant threats to human security.

In the last few decades, two main factors have shaped immigration policies and priorities of states. The first factor is the increased flow of goods, capital, ideas, and information because of globalization. Later, labor markets became international and new opportunities opened in potential destination countries for the increasing supply of both skilled and unskilled migrants from less developed source countries. For labor sending countries, urbanization, rural-to-urban migration, increasing working-age population, increasing education, increasing income inequalities and environmental change have become key factors influencing a person's decision to migrate (I Goldin, G Cameron, and M Balarajan, 2011, p. 153)).

At the same time, for the workforce, demographic changes, particularly depopulation and population aging, combined with workforce and skills shortages, have created employment incentives for migrant workers (G Hugo, 2008, pp. 3–12.) Transport and communication technology distances and destination countries. social networks are expanding. Moreover, all this has taken place against the backdrop of a broader set of tightened immigration policies and border controls to manage immigration. The concept of managed migration brings us to the

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second factor, the growing concern about security issues, including transnational crime and terrorism. After the September 11, 2001, attacks, policy makers identified immigrants as a potential security risk. It is no coincidence that it was concluded that migration must be managed effectively because national security is at stake. The regulation of borders has emerged to keep unwanted, high-risk migrants away from potential destination countries (I Goldin, G Cameron, and M Balarajan, op. cit. p. 121.). New surveillance and biometric technologies for border control, including fingerprint, iris recognition, and face scanning, have developed, making fraudulent trips difficult to fabricate. Borders have also begun to change, and in some cases, states have developed systems that allow for better information exchange (Bridget Anderson 2013, p. 88 & pp. 115—136.). In parallel, states have argued that in the era of globalization, such measures would be invaluable in tackling transnational crimes such as human trafficking and migrant smuggling (A Downer, 'Australia Leads the Way on Passport Biometrics', Media Release, 4 June 2003.). As a result, smuggling and smuggling are increasingly defined as border security issues. This discussion of border control and human trafficking lies within the broader nexus of globalization and the securitization of migration.

5. UNODC's Perspective

Although trafficking in human beings falls under the authority of various international organizations, the issue of border control in anti-trafficking responses creates an interesting debate from the perspective of the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC). On the one hand, UNODC is the only UN agency that focuses on the criminal justice element of human trafficking and migrant smuggling. As a result, border management is an important programming area. In addition to the UN Convention Against Transnational Organized Crime, UNODC is the guardian of the UN Protocol on the Prevention, Suppression and Punishment of Trafficking in Persons (Trafficking Protocol) and the UN Protocol Against Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea, and Air (Smuggling Protocol). fully supports States parties in strengthening border controls to prevent and detect human trafficking and migrant smuggling, as set out in Article 11 of both Protocols.

On the other hand, UNODC acknowledges that this claim is highly political and controversial. Critics argue that debates about sovereignty and nationalism are not fundamental reasons why states control immigration. On the contrary, they argue that overly restrictive immigration policies and tighter border controls result in serious political, economic, social, and human costs for both states and immigrants.

Another common criticism is that security agendas are accompanied by the marginalization of immigrants' human rights¹. While expressed in relation to broader immigration policies, such debates are beginning to foster wider dialogue about the role of border controls in anti-trafficking responses (A Schloenhardt, 23, 2012, p. 25). The perspective of this article will be slightly different from the mainstream, where much of the literature criticizes not only border controls but also criminal justice intervention in human trafficking. It is necessary to suggest that it is possible for states to combine tightly managed immigration systems and tight border controls with the protection of human rights, first by examining some of the tensions and contradictions that have arisen in this debate, and secondly, by arguing our argument against criticism. It has been made by critics of tighter border controls and security frameworks.

Consequently, it is pertinent to offer suggestions for consideration and further discussion on how states can reconcile what may be seen as conflicting agendas to develop more effective anti-trafficking interventions.

6. Controlling the Boundaries

Are sovereign states losing control in a globalizing world? There is a large literature on the changing nature of the state and the erosion of state sovereignty. For some, the growing concern about border control in relation to immigration reflects a decline in state power in the era of globalization (S Sassen, *Losing Control?* 2008, p. 199—215.) One scholar, Melissa Lane, argues that states control as well as their own power. argues that they should also accept the

¹Article 11:1 of the UN Protocol against the Smuggling of Migrants by Land, Sea, and Air states: 'Without prejudice to international commitments in relation to the free movement of people, States Parties shall strengthen, to the extent possible, such border controls as may be necessary to prevent and detect the smuggling of migrants.' Similarly, Article 11:1 of the UN Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons states: 'Without prejudice to international commitments in relation to the free movement of people, States Parties shall, to the extent possible, such border controls as may be necessary to prevent and detect trafficking in persons.'

limits of their abilities. This situation stemming from immigration in general and irregular immigration also argues that the concepts of sovereignty and nationalism are conditional arguments for greater state control over immigration. Forces push people to migrate. Therefore, states will never be successful in their attempts to control immigration. Then there is a constant tension between the interests of states and those of immigrants (M Lane, op. cit.).

Others must be viewed in the context of restrictive government immigration regimes and border control policies of immigration decision. Cross-border smuggling is commensurate with increasing demands for covert immigration services, including the provision of fake passports and visas, and the regulation of fraudulent employment opportunities. As a result, journeys are becoming more dangerous and thousands of migrants die each year trying to make unauthorized border crossings (J O'Connell Davidson, 2012, p. 32 & p. 39; G Hugo, pp. 22—24).

This theory holds weight, as we see that the market for covert immigration services is at least in part linked to expanding borders . Special mention should be made of surveillance, which is aimed at preventing irregular migrants from entering or residing in destination countries (I Goldin, G Cameron, and M Balarajan, p. 121).

Because immigrants believe their lives can be improved through immigration, people seek the services of third parties who want to facilitate both regular and irregular forms. Just as critics have suggested, studies of migration conducted by UNODC and others have shown that much of migration in Asia, and indeed worldwide, is facilitated and even initiated by third parties (UNODC, Bangkok, 2012; G Hugo, op. cit.).

Immigrants around the world often look for third parties that are directly or indirectly known to them and known to them. It is part of a locally established network to achieve its goals. Often these individuals are not human traffickers but small-scale smugglers – friends, relatives, acquaintances, or migrant workers – with established links between source and destination countries. However, many immigrants turn to third parties, endangering their savings, health, and safety. Moreover, large numbers of people are placed in exploitative situations, where their well-being, rights and lives are at serious threat (K Tamas and J Palme, p. 3).

To understand all this, it is sufficient to look at the Australian government's efforts to combat migrant smuggling by sea. The human, social and economic costs for both states and

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immigrants could be exacerbated by the same policies and measures aimed at solving the problem. Even the 'legal' recruitment and migration processes have become increasingly complex due to the involvement of third parties (G Hugo, Asia Pacific Memo, 2012, retrieved 10 January 2013).

A worrying trend in formal workforce programs has been that migrants have born increased transaction costs themselves, and brokers and private agents have made huge profits. For example, although the Thai Government establishes formal immigration schemes from Cambodia, Lao PDR, and Myanmar, these tend to be slower, less flexible, and more expensive than informal arrangements, a situation driven by excessive intermediaries' fees. Under these official schemes, agents (recruitment agencies) in sending countries and Thailand are responsible for recruiting and registering migrant workers, arranging pre-departure orientation, and training, and mediating labor disputes between workers and employers. Governments, in general, are not involved in the processes. Moreover, the system is neither highly regulated nor transparent, making it easy for both authorized and unauthorized recruitment agencies to take advantage of immigrants who understand little about the complex and time-consuming application procedures .

Although official immigration schemes aim to prevent migrant workers from paying excessive wages, the actual cost of formal recruitment is high, far higher than the costs associated with irregular forms of immigration (S Chantavanich, 2008). For example, brokerage fees are estimated to be paid for a passport. Under Thailand's national verification scheme, which allows irregular migrant workers in Thailand to gain legal status through the issuance of temporary passports, it was equivalent to US\$ 500-700 per passport, i.e., several months' salaries (Interview, A Hall, IPSR Foreign Expert, Mahidol University, 11 January 2013).

Immigrants, from Cambodia, Lao PDR, and Myanmar, have no choice but to take out large loans to cover costs. As Graeme Hugo points out, the immigration industry continues to grow and the main problem with regular and irregular systems is excessive rent-taking in both source and destination countries (G Hugo, p. 42). ("Managing Migration: Is border control fundamental to anti-trafficking ...")

Immigrants are vulnerable to exploitation, exploitation, and trafficking, and this is partly due to the costs of migration and the involvement of third parties, which often leaves them with leveraged debt situations. Research on Trafficking in Persons conducted by the United Nations Inter-Agency Project (UNIAP) has found that debt bondage and the use of intermediaries significantly increase the risk of exploitation and trafficking. Data on Cambodians deported from Thailand showed that male immigrants were twice as likely to be deceived or trafficked than female immigrants. The main reason for this was that the risk of being exploited or trafficked increased one and a half times for each broker and man involved (United Nations Inter-Agency Project (UNIAP) on Human Trafficking, 2010, p. 49). However, when much of the problem is related to third-party involvement, excessive rent-seeking, corruption and mismanagement, the question arises what role should border controls play in tackling the problem.

7. Migration Systems

For many observers, restrictive borders and immigration systems are the problem, not the solution. Alongside traffickers, critics argue that states are the main violators of immigrants' human rights. Front-line border and immigration officers are often involved in or complicit in the above-mentioned activities. Moreover, thousands of immigrants are detained for extended periods each year as authorities try to determine whether a person is a smuggler, trafficking, or asylum seeker .

At the very least, states fail to prevent and protect human rights violations. In each of these ways, the state has hindered human rights, as critics have noted.

8. The Primary Responsibility for Human Rights lies with the State

To what extent this logic is valid it does not go far enough. For it is also true that genuine human rights protections for immigrants, smuggled or not, can only be exercised and supported by sovereign states or intergovernmental and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) collaborating with them. The primary responsibility for addressing human trafficking and

protecting the human rights of migrant's rests with the state. This is the reality that a viable and meaningful discussion of the role of border controls in the fight against human trafficking must consider. Ignoring or denying this will only serve to make the current situation worse. States will not open their borders to the free movement of immigrants, no matter how much they are criticized. Even if one admits to losing control of states, it is extremely important, as Will Kymlicka argues, to have a sense of control over one's border.

- a. *By reducing fear, it makes citizens feel safe and takes away some of the heat in the area.*
- b. *In most countries, there is little support for large-scale migration, as well as a strong moral objection to rewarding irregular migrants who enter under false pretenses.*
- c. *Immigrants are easier to integrate into countries such as Australia and Canada, where immigration is governed and is a result of state choice, as large numbers of irregular migrants often result in a backlash against multiculturalism.*

Why border controls should play a role on their own in combating human trafficking; rather, it shows that sovereignty and nationalism are still strong norms influencing border controls and immigration policies. However, although the overall relationship between border controls, regulated immigration systems, human trafficking and human rights is evaluated, the following analysis and recommendations are built on a premise that few critics can dispute. Border controls around the world fail to prevent and detect human trafficking. However, this needs to be fixed.

9. Turkey Perspective

Considering that it is the sovereign right of every state to control its borders and regulate immigration, it is imperative that we see how the human rights of immigrants can fit into Turkey's real policy. Our answer to this question is clear. States have often adopted a criminal justice approach to addressing human trafficking. The basic principles that form the basis of this approach are included in the Protocols on Trafficking in Persons and Smuggling, as well as in other international agreements such as the Council of Europe Convention on Action

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against Trafficking in Human Beings. As of September 2013, 117 countries have ratified the Trafficking Protocol, which requires states to criminalize all forms of trafficking, prosecute and punish traffickers, strengthen national borders to combat the problem, encourage cooperation between states, and protect and assist victims.

As Chantal Thomas argues, 'These international instruments suggest that states do not relinquish their sovereign territorial concession - they use it to enhance international law rather than hinder it. Because both Protocols recognize the sovereign rights of states to control their borders and regulate immigration. UNODC fully supports this position and, as part of its mandate, works with states to promote adherence to the two Protocols and assist states in their implementation. ("Antitrafficking Review Issue2 | Human Trafficking | Immigration") Admittedly, the anti-trafficking frameworks developed by some states are more about political privileges than the legal obligations of the Trafficking Protocol. However, as Gallagher and Holmes point out, 'Achieving general agreement about the nature of the problem [trafficking] and the direction and extent of necessary solutions is widely lauded as evidence of real and tangible progress. This document is a clear sign that human trafficking is a criminal justice issue, of which border controls are an important part, at least in the eyes of states.

To some, weak support for the UN Convention on the Protection of the Rights of All Migrant Workers, as Susan Kneebone has pointed out, implies that 'when a rights dialogue fails, a security-criminal justice dialogue succeeds' . Despite supporting states, significant practical difficulties remain in achieving this effectively and with a human rights approach, according to the Trafficking Protocol and its Article 11, which mandates strengthening of border controls to prevent and detect trafficking in human beings.

10. What Are Possible Ways Forward for Negotiation and Discussion?

First, we need to address the practical barriers faced by states in translating their Protocol obligations into effective action, particularly about border controls and managed immigration systems. Below are a few key constraints faced by states, with some suggestions for consideration and further discussion on how they can reconcile the protection of human rights with tightly managed immigration systems and strict border controls in the current globalization

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context. But change does not happen in the short run; therefore, the following recommendations are some actions that should be prioritized. In this context, it is necessary to join the criticism that victims of trafficking are more likely to be identified as victims of trafficking violators.

One of the main reasons for this stems from the definition of human trafficking in the Trafficking Protocol. The definition does not offer a clear distinction between the experiences of victims of trafficking and the experiences of other immigrant groups. On the contrary, smuggling is seen as a subset of irregular migration and as a different phenomenon from smuggling. Connections and overlaps are overlooked because the two Protocols make a clear distinction between the two phenomena. (“Managing Migration: Is border control fundamental to anti-trafficking ...”) However, because trafficking practices are entwined with smuggling, which is particularly evident in the Southeast Asian region, it is often difficult for border officials to distinguish between victims of trafficking and undocumented immigrants. There is then a tendency to label and treat them all as irregular or undocumented immigrants, which typically results in deportation even if the immigrants are trafficked. Based on the facts described above, one solution being lobbied in the United Kingdom (UK) is the appointment of a non-partisan Anti-Trafficking Commissioner to bring consistency and accountability to government interventions.

The report, published in March 2013, also recommended establishing a single competent authority to oversee victim identity. Both recommendations offer potential solutions to structural problems. In addition to increased calls for surveillance, the report also found evidence that victims can be accurately identified at border controls, provided staff understand that a trafficked person is primarily a victim and not an illegal immigrant .

In this context, the need for well-trained, experienced front line and immigration officers cannot be underestimated. Still, education as an effective intervention in the fight against human trafficking remains highly controversial. The system is one in which frontline authorities (i.e., the state) decide the status of the migrant, particularly whether they are victims of trafficking or not. From the critics' point of view, the system suffers from serious flaws. Because each state decides for itself whether a particular immigrant receives assistance or is deported, critics argue that the system itself adds to their vulnerability. Regardless of whether they are smuggled in or not, given their socio-legal status, immigrants will constantly fear frontline officials.

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Education will never solve this structural problem. However, as the state decides who counts as a trafficking victim, it is crucial that frontline officers have the appropriate knowledge and skills; otherwise, all victims of trafficking will be defined as irregular migrants. In our experience, frontline workers are often poorly equipped to identify and assist victims. This is partly due to the links and overlaps of human trafficking and smuggling. But it also reflects a general lack of understanding that human trafficking and migrant smuggling are part of the continuum in the migration process, and that a person who is smuggled one day can become a victim of trafficking the next. For border and immigration officials to perform their duties effectively, they need ongoing support, resources, training, and counselling, not only to identify and assist victims, but also to protect evidence and manage the initial stages of investigations in suspected trafficking cases, including detention. they have needs. Gallagher and Holmes state that the Council of Europe Convention on Action against Trafficking in Human Beings clearly states that accurate identification of victims is critical to protection and assistance provisions, and failure in this regard will lead to denial of human rights. The identity and protection procedures of frontline border and immigration officers should be regularly independently evaluated (for example, by an impartial Anti-Trafficking Commissioner) to ensure they are responsive, consistent, and transparent .

Greater interaction with frontline border and immigration authorities (for example, through training and capacity building activities) in the Southeast Asian region has opened opportunities for organizations like UNODC as well as NGOs to influence and advance human rights. State authorities are in greater contact with organizations that advocate for the rights of trafficked and smuggled migrants. Whether this improves the rights of migrants is debatable, but there is at least the potential to integrate human rights concerns into frontline border control and immigration work.

Another main limitation is the lack of appropriate resources to effectively manage migration. For example, not all states have the resources of the United States government, which spent approximately \$18 billion on federal immigration practices in fiscal 2012. This amount is 24% higher than the 2013 combined budgets of the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI), the Drug Enforcement Administration, the Secret Service, the U.S. Police Service, and the Bureau of Alcohol, Tobacco, Firearms and Explosives.

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Border control at points of entry has become effective, but MPI has also recognized that enforcement alone is not sufficient to effectively deal with the broader challenges posed to the state by both regular and irregular migration. There is a crucial point here. Border controls and managed migration systems have a role to play in combating trafficking but should be seen as only part of a multifaceted and comprehensive approach to trafficking. While the details are beyond the scope of this discussion, other elements are also critical. However, it would be fair to recommend that states maximize the resources available to border and immigration enforcement, especially for the protection of victims of trafficking, but also especially for victims of trafficking. Human rights of immigrants in general. This goal is crucial for an effective anti-trafficking response that includes tightened borders and regulated immigration systems. Protection resources can be maximized by adding added resources to the system and making better use of existing resources. All states under both Protocols have a legal obligation to protect the rights of trafficked and smuggled migrants. Increased resources and appropriate training on how to protect the human rights of all migrants, not just victims of trafficking, are positive starting points. This recommendation is followed by the need to improve the governance of migration systems in both source and destination countries.

Institutional mechanisms can be developed to protect migrant workers, including frameworks to ensure that migrant workers' rights are protected, recruitment agencies are licensed and regulated, bilateral agreements are negotiated, and migrant workers are trained before they leave. Some states have enacted such measures; yet they fail to protect immigrants from abuse and exploitation. A main reason for this is vested interests in maintaining existing systems of exploitation for corruption and financial gain.

Tackling these systemic issues of corruption, third-party involvement and mismanagement of immigration systems will be difficult, but is there really an alternative? Policies Based on Empirical Evidence A final major limitation that needs to be addressed is the lack of timely, comprehensive, and accurate data on the extent and scale of human trafficking and migrant smuggling. Data collection systems are inconsistent across countries and are often not protected in a way that makes information suitable for analysis.

Reliable data are needed to systematically analyze the causes, dynamics and impact of migrant smuggling and human trafficking in countries of origin, transit, and destination. In this context,

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border and immigration officers have important duties in intelligence gathering. Some countries' analytical and research capacities need to be developed, but evidence-based knowledge is essential to develop effective policies and countermeasures against human trafficking and migrant smuggling. Improved research and data collection will strengthen more initiative-taking, comprehensive and informed policies, and responses. (“View of Managing Migration: Is border control fundamental to anti ...”) Indeed, critics are right to say that restrictive immigration policies and border controls are often based not on empirical evidence but on misinformation and pressure from interest groups:

Raise awareness of THB and SoM among all key stakeholders, including law enforcement, the judiciary, healthcare professionals and labor inspectors, among others, by providing information and training;

- i. *Promote cross-border and international cooperation between countries of origin, transit, and destination through Bilateral Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) and a special focus on South-South cooperation;*
- ii. *Improve data collection on THB and SoM as a prerequisite for evidence-based policy action;*
- iii. *Promote a victim-centred, human rights-based, gender-sensitive approach to ensure the protection and identification of victims, in full cooperation with NGOs;*
- iv. *Dismantle criminal networks through financial surveillance and fight corruption among public officials and prosecute traffickers and smugglers to avoid impunity;*
- v. *Improve national level coordination among multisectoral service providers working in the field of human trafficking and migrant smuggling;*
- vi. *Addressing the demand that drives migrant smuggling and human trafficking, including awareness raising, monitoring supply chains and private sector involvement in direct accountability.*

These ACP-EU Dialogue on Migration and Development recommendations reflect pillars of international best practice in addressing both crimes and guide the priorities and focal points of

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technical support provided by Action. Therefore, they form the organizational structure of this report. Human smuggling and human trafficking are serious crimes that can be committed by land, air, sea, or a combination of these.

These are different but sometimes related crimes that must be clearly understood if effective responses are to be made against them. Internationally accepted definitions of these crimes are included in two separate documents, the Immigrant Smuggling Protocol, and the Human Trafficking Protocol, which complement the United Nations Convention on Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC). “Immigrant smuggling” (also referred to as migrant smuggling or human smuggling) is defined in article 3(a) of the Immigrant Smuggling Protocol as follows:

“Benefit from illegal entry into a State Party of which he is not a national or permanent resident.”

In Article 3(a) of the Trafficking Protocol, “trafficking” (also referred to as human trafficking) is defined as:

“The supply, transportation, transfer, harboring, or receipt of persons by threat or use. (“CHAPTER 5: MIGRATION FLOWS - Miami Beach Senior High School”) “(for the purpose of exploitation) to give or receive payment or benefit by force, kidnapping, cheating, deception, abuse of power, or exploiting the helplessness of a person, or to gain the consent of a person who has control over another.”

Exploitation shall, as a minimum, include the exploitation of the prostitution of others or other forms of sexual exploitation, forced labor or services, bondage or similar practices, servitude, or the removal of organs. (“Rule of Law, Law, Prostitution, Environment ... - Ask Lawyers”)

From these definitions, human trafficking consists of three elements:

- vii. *An act (hiring, moving, transporting, hosting, or receiving people)*
- viii. *Giving or receiving payments or benefits by means (the threat of force or use of force or other forms of coercion, kidnapping), fraud, deception, abuse of power or vulnerability, or to obtain the consent of a person who has control over another person,*

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In contrast, the crime of migrant smuggling consists of two elements:

In the last decade, regional conflicts, political instability and repression, poverty and the impact of climate change have resulted in an increased number of migrants and refugees seeking to relocate. This has led to numerous crises linked to the illegal smuggling of migrants and has resulted in thousands of deaths. Every year, millions of migrants in search of a better future put their lives in the hands of migrant smugglers who see them as an opportunity to make huge financial gains. While the exact amount of revenues generated is difficult to quantify, recent increases in immigration could mean annual revenues currently exceed \$10 billion.

- b. *Immigrant smuggling has increased in recent years, but the number of smugglers arrested is still exceptionally low. Many countries do not consider migrant smuggling to be an 'elevated risk' crime for money laundering and only very few investigations or prosecutions are initiated or concluded. This is due to a few factors, including the lack of effective international cooperation and often a lack of focus and resources to support a 'follow the money' approach. ("Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing Risks Arising from Migrant ...")*
- c. *An informal money transfer system known as hawala is the most common method of transferring funds from migrant smuggling between jurisdictions. This makes it extremely difficult for law enforcement to conduct financial investigations. Other methods involve physical transportation of funds via cash couriers or money mules. ("New perspectives: Nexus between smuggling of migrants and terrorism")*
- d. *In recent years, smugglers have started to use social media and encrypted digital communication services widely in their recruitment and coordination activities. ("Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing Risks Arising from Migrant ...") While this provides smugglers with opportunities to increase their efficiency, it also provides law enforcement opportunities to detect and monitor smugglers' activities, including financial flows.*
- e. *Migrant smuggling groups increasingly also outsource their money laundering activities to professional laundering networks.*

- f. *In general, there is limited information on the links between terrorist financing and migrant smuggling. However, there is evidence that terrorists receive money from smugglers along various African migration routes in the form of 'tolls' for safe passage through the territory they control and is linked to the facilitation of FTFs.*
- g. *Many countries have difficulty understanding the money laundering/TF risks arising from migrant smuggling. While some countries have access to qualified information and case studies, a sizable percentage of countries are unable to provide complete statistics on aspects of the performance of their AML/CFT systems in relation to smuggling of migrants.*
- h. *Immigrant smuggling is an international crime, but national and international cooperation between relevant authorities has been challenging for many countries. To prevent migrant smuggling, countries need to proactively track money linked to migrant smuggling. The report identifies a set of good practices and recommendations. These include strengthening inter-agency, international and regional cooperation, with a particular focus on supporting countries directly affected by migrant smuggling.*
- i. *The report also highlights the importance of strengthening cooperation with the private sector and providing them with guidance and information on the specific methods used by smugglers to transfer and conceal revenues. (“FATF REPORT Money Laundering and Terrorist Financing Risks Arising from ...”) Financial institutions, and in particular banks and money or value transfer services, have a key role to play in providing accurate and targeted reporting of suspicious transactions that can help authorities profile the financial behavior of migrant smugglers. Immigrant smuggling may not generate large sums compared to other major transnational crimes, but it often causes serious physical harm and suffering. Countries need to act to be more effective at tracking, disrupting, and recovering illegal earnings that encourage criminals to smuggle migrants.*

11. Conclusion

is still much we do not know about human trafficking and human smuggling as it affects Europe ? This is not surprising in view of the latent nature of the phenomena. The research agenda outlined here should only be seen as a start. Most commentators agree that human trafficking and human smuggling are best analyzed in business terms. There are some fundamental aspects of the commercial organization of human trafficking that need to be explored. First, more research is needed on how the human trafficking industry has evolved. While it is unclear how far this analogy should be taken, it is reasonable to assume that it will share many characteristics with legitimate businesses. For example, there are likely to be differences between legitimate and illegitimate governance structures, especially given the need for tight security in trafficking organizations. Currently, human trafficking consists of both large and small businesses, but there is no information yet on how they interact and how likely rationalization through franchises, acquisitions and collaborations is. As new niche businesses develop, we need to know whether they are standalone or part of larger operations. It is also possible for new and distinctive trafficker roles to develop. The nature of the markets developed and served by traffickers and undocumented immigrants should be investigated to determine whether new ones are emerging in Europe and how their potential is being exploited. For example, niche markets such as prostitution, trade in production shops, and ethnic economic enclaves need to be defined and analyzed in commercial terms.

It is necessary to define the concept of organized crime more sharply and to take a closer look at how much it participates in human trafficking. Okólski's article in this volume, for example, strongly shows that the relationship is far from simple. Human trafficking may be just one of several nefarious business interests in the portfolios of organized groups, and there may be competition between these interests. We have little idea how dominant business trafficking is for such organisations. In addition, information communication and technology (ICT) is openly used by these organizations, but it is not yet known how and to what extent the World Wide Web is used for recruitment, communication, and management. Implications for migration policy Human trafficking and illegal migration can interact significantly with broader migration policy in general, and research is needed to determine whether this interaction itself initiates change in national migration policies and, if so, in what direction. As part of this process, we need to identify more clearly how the priority of

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ensuring national security (the state that controls its borders and citizenship) conflicts with ensuring the security of the individual (providing basic human rights) and ensuring success

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- As Bridget Anderson notes, border control is not just about conditions of entry, but also about conditions of stay. Border enforcement has also shifted 'inland' (eg, through tightened employer regulations and penalties, increased workplace inspections, removals of overstayers). For a detailed analysis, see: B Anderson, *Us and Them? ("Antitrafficking Review Issue2 | Human Trafficking | Immigration")* "The dangerous politics of immigration control, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2013, p. 88 & pp. 115—136." ("Managing Migration: Is border control fundamental to anti-trafficking ...") ("Managing Migration: Is border control fundamental to anti-trafficking ...")
- At the inter-state level, it is by no means clear how migration relations between European states are affected by trafficking and human smuggling, whether they are harmed or if constructive dialogue occurs and whether there is a spill over into other areas of relations. International agreements are urging the need for exchange of information, but it is yet unknown how freely states engage in

this and how inter-state cooperation compares in efficiency with cooperation within and between trafficking organizations. It could be that states are at a disadvantage because they operate as discrete units with collaborative (and slow) response structures.

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G Hugo, 'Demographic Change and Labor Mobility in the Asia-Pacific – Implications for business and regional economic integration: Synthesis' in G Hugo and S Young, *Labor Mobility in the Asia-Pacific Region: Dynamics, issues, and a new APEC agenda : A survey and analyzes of governance challenges on labor migration for APEC economies*, Institute of Southeast Asian Studies, Singapore, 2008, pp. 3—12.

G Hugo, p. 23; also see: S Molland, 'Is 'Safe Migration' Along the Thai-Lao Border Truly 'Safe'?', *Asia Pacific Memo*, 2012, <http://www.asiapacificmemo.ca/is-safe-migration-along-the-thai-lao-border-truly-safe>. (“Antitrafficking Review Issue2 | Human Trafficking | Immigration”) (“Antitrafficking Review Issue2 | Human Trafficking | Immigration”)

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GSN/ILHR (Global Survival
Network/International League for
Human Rights)

"I Goldin, G Cameron and M Balarajan,
Exceptional People: How migration
shaped our work and will define our
future, Princeton University Press,
Princeton, 2011, p. 153; pp. 214—
241." ("Managing Migration: Is
border control fundamental to anti-
trafficking ...") ("Managing
Migration: Is border control
fundamental to anti-trafficking ...")

To obtain answers to these questions, the
old academic chestnut "we need more
research" applies a fortiori.
Comprehensive surveys are urgently
needed for Western European
countries like those conducted further
east and using the same methodology.
In that way, the experiences of
individual countries, geographically
located in unusual parts of Europe's
trafficking/smuggling system, can be
used as lenses to allow us to see more
clearly what is going on.

IOM/TCC/ICMPD (International
Organization for Migration/Technical
Cooperation Center for Europe and

Central Asia/International Center for
Migration Policy and Development)

J O'Connell Davidson, 'Absolving the State:
The trafficking-slavery metaphor',
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p. 32 & p. 39; G Hugo, pp. 22—24.

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knowledge is sobering at the least. The
research agenda set out here should be
seen as only the beginning. It is
presented for debate and not for
prescription.

Meese, J., K. Van Impe, and S. Vanheste,
1998 Multidisciplinary Research on
the Phenomenon of Trafficking in
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Most commentators agree that trafficking and human smuggling are best analyzed in business terms. There are some fundamental aspects of the business organization of trafficking that require investigation. First, further research is needed into how the trafficking industry is evolving. It is reasonable to assume that it will share many features with legitimate businesses although it is unclear how far this analogy should be taken. It is probable, for example, that there are differences between legitimate and illegitimate management structures, particularly given the need for tight security within trafficking organizations. At present, trafficking consists of both large and small businesses but there is yet no information on how these interact and how far rationalization is likely through franchises, take-overs, and cooperation. As new niche businesses develop, we need to know whether they are independent or part of larger operations. It is also possible that new and trafficker roles may develop.

Most of the research on trafficking focuses on how migrants get to their destinations. Except for those

working illegally in the sex trade, there is a dearth of information on the outcomes for most of the migrants involved. Little is currently known about how most trafficked migrants earn a livelihood, how the migration cycle ends for the trafficked/smuggled migrant, both in and out of debt bondage and what the relationship is between the apprehended individual and the criminal system at the destination.

OSCE (Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe)

S Sassen, *Losing Control? Sovereignty in an age of globalization*, Columbia University Press, New York, 1996. Also see: M Bosworth, 'Border Control and the Limits of the Sovereign State', *Social & Legal Studies*, vol. 17, no. 2, 2008, p. 199—215.

The concept of organized crime needs to be more sharply defined and a closer look taken at how far it participates in trafficking. Okólski's paper in this volume, for example, indicates strongly that the relationship is anything but straightforward. Trafficking may be only one of a

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series of nefarious business interests within the portfolios of organized groups and there may be competition between these interests. We have little idea how far trafficking in people is the dominant business for such organizations. Furthermore, information communication and technology (ICT) is clearly being used by these organizations, but it is not yet known how and to what extent the World Wide Web is being used for recruitment, communication, and management.

The nature of the markets being developed and served by traffickers and illegal migrants need to be investigated to determine whether new ones are emerging within Europe and how their potential is being tapped. For example, niche markets, such as prostitution, trafficking into manufacturing sweatshops and ethnic economic enclaves need to be identified and analyzed in business terms.

There is much that we still do not know about trafficking and human smuggling as they affect Europe. This is not surprising in view of the covert

nature of the phenomena. However, given their high profile on the political agendas of both the European Union and individual states, the lack of basic

Trafficking and human smuggling: a European perspective 49

Trafficking and illegal migration may interact significantly with broader migration policy and research needs to be done to determine whether this interaction itself initiates change in national immigration policies

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